

Finite Element Analysis of Tapered Laminated Composite Plates
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ABSTRACT

A finite element computer program was developed to perform the stress analysis of tapered laminated composite plates using a personal computer. The objective for developing this program is to obtain numerical solutions to the mechanical response of tapered laminated composite plates. The finite element derivation was based on the balance of internal and external energies using the equations of the lamination theory. To model the composite plate, four-noded (2-D) rectangular elements with five degrees of freedom for each node were used. Since the thickness, stacking sequence, and stiffness vary from location to location in the tapered laminate, special considerations were given to the construction of the element stiffness matrix.

Both the classical and approximate solutions for various plate and beam problems were used to evaluate the accuracy of the finite element program. This includes the use of the solutions for the bending of isotropic and laminated composite (flat) plates. In this regard, the maximum error between the analytical solutions and the finite element results was less than 2 percents. The approximate solutions (deflections) to the bending of the tapered laminated composite plates was obtained using the moment-area method of the beam theory. A deviation of 9 percents was found between this approximate solution and the finite element results. It should be pointed out that the finite element program gives a rather quick convergence to an asymptotic solution when the number of elements are increased. It is believed that this finite element computer program can provide an accurate analysis of the response of tapered laminated composite plates.

KEYWORDS: finite element analysis; laminated plate theory; tapered laminates; flexural; plate element.

INTRODUCTION

With the absence of the 3-D brick element for orthotropic materials [1,2], the finite element analysis of tapered composite laminates is a very challenging task. Under such a restriction, a general laminate element containing a change of both stacking sequence and thickness must be used. Consequently, within an element, the element stiffness is no longer a constant and is not obtainable through a direct integration process. However, it is anticipated that there will be fewer general laminate elements needed than that of the 3-D orthotropic material brick elements to model the same structure. As a result, a finite element program utilizing the general laminate element may be more efficient in solution time for the complicated composite structure problems. In a general laminate element, the stiffness characteristics such as the extensional, coupling, and bending effects [3,4] must exist. In this regard, the lamination theory [3,4] should be incorporated in the formulation. Since the

stiffness matrices of a laminate element are defined in terms of the mid-plane of the element, the relation between the local and global stiffness matrices become very complicated. This problem may be resolved by introducing the concept of substructuring [5], or global-local modeling [6], or the laminated beam element [7].

The overall objective of this research program is to develop a finite element program contains tapered laminated brick elements. In this paper, a laminated plate element containing the characteristics of the change of stacking sequence and thickness is introduced. This is considered as the first step for the development of the tapered laminate brick element. The development of the tapered laminated plate element will resolve the local stiffness formulation problem. After this, the development of the tapered laminated brick element will require to establish the relationship between the local and global stiffness matrices.

FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

The 4-noded rectangular composite plate element developed in this project is considered to receive both the in-plane loads (F_x, F_y) and out-of-plane loads (F_z, M_x, M_y). As a result, there will be five degrees of freedom at each node. The corresponding nodal deformations are the in-plane displacements, u and v , the out-of-plane displacement w and the rotations about the X and Y-axis, $\theta_x (= \partial w / \partial x)$ and $\theta_y (= \partial w / \partial y)$ (Fig. 1).

The displacements of the four nodal points can be represented by:

$$\{\delta\} = \{\delta', \delta''\}^T \quad (1)$$

where

$$\{\delta'\} = \{u_i, v_i\}^T$$

$$\{\delta''\} = \left\{ w_i, \frac{\partial w_i}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial w_i}{\partial x} \right\}^T$$

$$i = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

$\{\delta'\}$ and $\{\delta''\}$ are nodal in-plane displacement and out-of-plane displacement respectively.

Following the thin plate theory [3,4] assumptions, the in-plane displacements can be written as

$$u = u_o - z \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \quad (2)$$

$$v = v_o - z \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}$$

where u_o , v_o and w are the middle plane displacements of the x, y and z-axis respectively.

By applying the strain-displacement equations of elasticity, the strain components are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{ox} \\ \epsilon_{oy} \\ \gamma_{oxy} \end{Bmatrix} + Z \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{ox} \\ \epsilon_{oy} \\ \gamma_{oxy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = - \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \\ 2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The terms in equations (4) and (5) are referred to as the middle plane strain and the middle plane curvatures respectively.

To relate the nodal displacements to the displacement at any location within an element, the interpolation functions (displacement functions) must be assumed.

$$\{u, v\}^T = [N] \{u_i, v_i\}^T \quad (6)$$

where

$$[N] = \begin{bmatrix} N_1 & 0 & N_2 & 0 & N_3 & 0 & N_4 & 0 \\ 0 & N_1 & 0 & N_2 & 0 & N_3 & 0 & N_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

in which the interpolation functions, N_i 's are in terms of local coordinates ξ and η , defined in Fig. 2

$$N_1 = \frac{1}{4} (1-\xi) (1-\eta), \quad N_2 = \frac{1}{4} (1+\xi) (1-\eta)$$

$$N_3 = \frac{1}{4} (1+\xi) (1+\eta), \quad N_4 = \frac{1}{4} (1-\xi) (1+\eta)$$

From equation (6), the mid-plane strain components can be expressed in terms of nodal displacements,

$$\{\epsilon_o\} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{a} \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial \xi} \\ \frac{1}{b} \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial \eta} \\ \frac{1}{a} \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial \xi} + \frac{1}{b} \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial \eta} \end{bmatrix} \text{ or } [B'] \{u_i, v_i\}^T \quad (8)$$

Where $[B']$ is the partial differentiation operator matrix relating strain components to nodal displacements.

The function describing the out-of-plane displacement can be assumed by a fourth order polynomial,

$$w(\xi, \eta) = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 \xi + \alpha_3 \eta + \alpha_4 \xi^2 + \alpha_5 \xi \eta + \alpha_6 \eta^2 + \alpha_7 \xi^3 + \alpha_8 \xi^2 \eta + \alpha_9 \xi \eta^2 + \alpha_{10} \eta^3 + \alpha_{11} \xi^3 \eta + \alpha_{12} \xi \eta^3 \quad (9)$$

Substituting equation (9) into equation (5), the curvatures can be written as

$$\{\kappa\} = [G] \{\alpha_i\} \quad (10)$$

Where $[G]_{3 \times 12}$ is a differential operator matrix and $\{\alpha_i\}_{12 \times 1}$ is the coefficients of the out-of-plane displacement function.

The out-of-plane displacement function, w , can also be related to the out-of-plane nodal displacement as follows,

$$\{\delta''\} = [C] \{\alpha_i\} \quad (11)$$

or

$$\{\alpha_i\} = [C]^{-1} \{\delta''\}$$

where $[C]$ is a 12×12 matrix which depends only on the element geometry.

Substituting $\{\alpha_i\}$ in equation (11) into equation (10), we can get,

$$\{\kappa\} = [G] [C]^{-1} \{\delta''\} \stackrel{\text{or}}{=} [B''] \{\delta''\} \quad (12)$$

Combining equations (8) and (12), the mid-plane strains $\{\epsilon_o\}$ and curvatures $\{\kappa\}$ can be described by the nodal displacements,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_o \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B' & O \\ O & B'' \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta' \\ \delta'' \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Based on the lamination theory [3,4], the force $\{N\}$ and moment $\{M\}$ resultants are defined as,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_o \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

By replacing $\{\epsilon_o\}$ and $\{\kappa\}$ in equation (14) with equation (13), we can obtain the following;

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} B' & O \\ O & B'' \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta' \\ \delta'' \end{Bmatrix} \stackrel{\text{or}}{=} [D'] [B_o] \{\delta\} \quad (15)$$

Where $[A]$, $[B]$, and $[D]$ are the extensional, coupling and bending stiffness matrices of a composite laminate.

The internal work done by the force and moment resultants is the product of equations (13) and (15)

$$W_I = \iint \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_o \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} dx dy \quad (16)$$

Substituting equations (13) and (15) into (16), the internal work done is

$$W_I = \iint \{\delta\}^T [B_o]^T [D'] [B_o] \{\delta\} dx dy \quad (17)$$

In the absence of thermal loading and initial stresses, the total applied nodal forces in an element can be defined as

$$\{F\} = \left\{ (F_u, F_v)_i, (F_w, M_x, M_y)_i \right\}_{i=1, 2, 3, 4}^T \quad (18)$$

Consequently, the total external work done can be expressed as

$$W_E = \{\delta\}^T \{F\} \quad (19)$$

In a static equilibrium condition, the internal energy must be balanced with the external energy,

$$\iint \{\delta\}^T [B_o]^T [D'] [B_o] \{\delta\} dx dy = \{\delta\}^T \{F\} \quad (20)$$

Based on equation (20), we can define the stiffness matrix for a 4-noded composite element as follows,

$$[k_e] = ab \iint [B_o]^T [D'] [B_o] d\xi d\eta \quad (21)$$

MODIFICATION OF STIFFNESS MATRIX

The derivations presented in the previous section are essentially applicable to analyze flat laminated composite plates. For the tapered composite laminates, a modification to the stiffness matrix $[k]$ is necessary. This is because that within an element the laminate stiffness matrices $[A]$, $[B]$, and $[D]$ are not constants due to the continuous change of thickness and stacking sequence. To adjust for this, three methods were used. The first method is the average method which simply takes the numerical average of the stiffness matrices (i.e. the summation of the stiffness matrices divided by 4) of the four nodal points of the element. This method should suffer somewhat due to the fact that the variation of the coupling ($[B]$) and bending ($[D]$) stiffness matrices are nonlinear along the length of the element. The second method is referred to as the "mean method" which takes the average of the stiffness matrices obtained from several sub-divisions within an element. It was thought that the mean method can account for the nonlinear variation and abruptly change (due to the change of stacking sequence) of stiffness more accurately than that of the average method. The third method for the stiffness modification is an integration method which requires an explicit expression for the variation of the stiffness along the length of an element. It should be pointed out that some difficulties will arise in the integration method if the tapered section of an element contains multiple layers with different fiber angle orientations. In this case, the analytical expression of the stiffness matrix will not be a continuous function and the numerical integration will be very difficult to carry out. As a result, in this research, the integration method only applied to the element having tapered section with one fiber angle orientation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A finite element computer program was developed based on the principles presented in the previous section. This program was written in FORTRAN 77 language and compiled with a personal computer. To verify the usefulness of this finite element program, some plate problems with either a closed-form or an approximate solution were used. The verification problems included the isotropic plate and anisotropic laminate plate under various loading and boundary conditions. What follows are the results of some of the tested cases.

The first example is a simply supported symmetric cross-ply flat laminate ($[0/90/0/90]_s$) under uniformly distributed pressure. The dimensions of the plate are 304.8 mm x 304.8 mm x 20.3 mm. The thickness of each layer was assumed as 2.54 mm. The orthotropic material properties of each layer were $E_1 = 310$ GPa, $E_2 = 124$ GPa, $G_{12} = 60$ GPa, and $\nu_{12} = 0.23$. The uniformly distributed pressure was assumed to be 1.72 MPa. The theoretical solution was obtained using the Navier's method. Fig. 3 shows the comparison between the theory and the finite element solution. Basically, the plate was modeled by two rows of elements parallel along the axial direction. The element

number in Fig. 3 reveals the total number of elements used. It was found that the finite element solution converged to the theoretical solution and gave an error of less than 2% for a moderate number of elements used.

The second example is a tapered isotropic cantilever plate (76.2 mm wide and 457.2 mm long) with a concentrated force (=222 N) applied at the center location of the free end. The Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio were assumed as 276 GPa and 0.23 respectively. The thickness at the free end was 15.2 mm and the thickness at the fixed end was 25.4 mm. Fig. 4 gives the comparison between the analytical and finite element solutions for the deflection under the applied load. The analytical solution, in this case, was obtained through the moment area method [8] of the beam theory. In Fig. 4, the finite element solution obtained through the use of different number of elements are also given. It was found that the finite element solution converged to the analytical solution quite rapidly. In this case, less than 1% percent deviation between the analytical and finite element solutions was obtained.

The third example is a symmetric tapered laminated composite cantilever plate subjected to a concentrated force. The tapered laminate has the same geometry and applied load as that used in the second example. On the other hand, the material properties are the same as that used in the first example. The stacking sequences at the free end and the fixed end of the plate are $[15/30/45]_s$ and $[60/60/15/30/45]_s$ respectively. The composite laminate was modeled by the same way that used in the second example. The moment area method was used to obtain an approximate solution for this example. In this regard, the coupling effect between bending and twisting actions was ignored. The three stiffness matrix modification techniques were used in this problem. In particular, five sub-sections were used in the mean method to model the element stiffness matrix. The comparison between the approximate and finite element solutions is shown in Fig. 5. It was found that the average method had a slower convergence than that of the mean method and integration method. In fact, in this case, the mean method and the integration method gave practically the same result. The results obtained from the mean method and integration method had a 9% deviation from that of the moment area method. It appeared that in order to obtain convergence more than one element was needed for each tapered step. Fig. 6 shows a plot of deformed shape (obtained from the finite element solution) versus the undeformed geometry of this example problem. It should be pointed out that the deflection is slightly unsymmetrical with respect to the center line. This is due to the existence of the bending-twisting coupling effect (i.e. D_{16} , D_{26} are non-zero).

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the finite element procedure using a 2-D plate element for analyzing tapered laminated composite was introduced. It appears that such a formulation can be used to obtain excellent results provided that special care must be taken to construct the stiffness matrix. With the absence of the concern regarding the failure process due to the interlaminar stresses, the finite element program developed in this research will serve as a rapid and accurate analysis tool for composite laminates with tapered section and change in stacking sequence.

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Fig. 1 The nodal forces and deformations of a flat plate element.

Fig. 2 Transformation from global to local axes.

Fig. 3 Comparison between theoretical and finite element solutions for the maximum deflection of a $[0/90/0/90]_s$ laminate.

Fig. 4 Comparison between approximate and finite element solutions for the maximum deflection of a tapered cantilever plate.

Fig. 5 Comparison between approximate and finite element solutions for the centerline deflection of a tapered laminate.

Fig. 6 The deflection profile of a tapered laminate.